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Changing the Nuclei

With Antimatter a specific proton or neutron can be eliminated from the nucleus to create a new atom. In the process the new atom attains its purest form. Like Weapons grade Uranium from Thorium or Highest quality Gold from Lead.

Positrons can be teleported from Black Hole intelligently with use of an AI to perform the nuclear reaction of creating new atoms.

Nuclear Dome is also attended using Geofencing of Positrons with Geospatial Intelligence System.

Bibliography:

Mohanty, S. (2026). Antimatter: The most useful and valuable commodity of the Universe. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18621108>

Mohanty, S. (2024). Teleporting Robotics in Space and Time. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14290194>

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